

Edge Finishing Effects on Transverse Cracking of Cross-Ply CFRP Laminates

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents experimental results on the edge finishing effects on transverse cracking in T800H/3631 [0₂/90₄]_s cross-ply CFRP laminates. Results show that a finer edge finish, which reduces the edge surface roughness and removes the edge defects, significantly delays the onset of transverse cracking and reduces the crack density. In addition, laminate failure strains decreased with the decreasing crack density. A qualitative discussion of the observation is also presented based on fracture mechanics. The importance of specimen preparation in a study of transverse crack will be emphasized.

1. INTRODUCTION

Transverse crack is typically the first damage that occurs in continuous fiber composite laminates under tensile load condition. The existence of transverse crack can alter mechanical properties such as strength, stiffness, and dimensional stability, besides laminate thermal, electrical, and acoustical properties. Therefore, accurate predictions of the onset and accumulation of the transverse crack as a function of load history is crucial to general structural application using a composite material.

So called *in situ* transverse strength effect has been studied extensively for type laminates subjected to constrained tension loads [1] [2] [3] [4]. It has been demonstrated that both structural characteristics (ex. component configurations, stacking sequence, ply group thickness, and hybridization) and material properties (ex. laminate moduli, hygrothermal expansion coefficients, and fracture toughness) affect a laminate's resistance to transverse crack. The formation of transverse crack within a lamina oriented in a particular direction depends on the total thickness and the constraint of neighboring fibers oriented in other directions.

However, a few studies of machining effects on transverse crack behavior of composite laminates have been reported [5] [6], although there are abundant literature of machining (ex. drilling, cutting and milling) induced damage in composite laminates [7] [8] [9].

This paper presents an experimental study of edge finishing effects on transverse crack behavior and ultimate strength of cross-ply CFRP laminates.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material system employed in this study was Toray T800H/3631 graphite-epoxy composite having 57% of fiber volume fraction.

Test specimen configuration is shown in Figure 1. All specimens were cut from an end-tabbed 12-ply [0₂/90₄]_S T800H/3631 laminate plate using diamond wheel cutter (grain size = #170). The cutting speed was 1600 m/min and the feeding rate was 200 mm/min. Then, the edges of the specimens except specimen (A), non-polished specimen, were differently polished by sandpapers or polishing powders. Summary of finishing conditions of the specimens are given in Table 1. They were specimen (B) = #80 sandpapered, specimen (C) = #400 sandpapered, and specimen (D) = polished with 5 and 0.05 μm Al₂O₃ powder after #1000 and #2000 sandpaper polish. Specimen (E) was mechanically edge finished by high speed milling and grinding. The depth of cut, the cutting speed, and the feeding speed of milling and grinding were 0.05 and 0.5 mm, 250 and 250 m/min, and 120 and 220 mm/min, respectively.

Maximum surface roughness (R_{max}) of specimen edges were measured by Mitsutoyo Surf-Test 201 (Mitsutoyo Corp.) having probe radius of 0.1 μm. Measurements of R_{max} were performed at six points in 90 degree layer of the specimen with the scanning length of 0.25 mm. Average values of R_{max} are shown in Table 1.

R_{max} and change of specimen width are shown in Figure 2. Polishing by sandpapers altered the edge roughness and reduced the width by removing damaged zone induced by diamond wheel cutting. Tensile tests were conducted by INSTRON 4208 Tensile Test Machine (INSTRON Corp.) with the cross head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Strain of a specimen was measured using two strain gages attached to the sample surfaces. The ambient temperature and the relative humidity were 23°C and 50%, respectively.

Damage was detected by a remote microscope, Keyence VH-5900 (Keyence Corp.) with the magnification of 50 to 1000. The damage state was on-line recorded in a videotape and off-line analyzed. This on-line damage detection technique does not require specimens remount which often causes specimen misalignment and multiple loading. The crack numbers were normalized by the total volume of 90 degree layers, or the crack density has a dimension of numbers per volume.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crack densities of differently edge finished specimens, (A), (B), (C), and (D) as a function of tensile strains are shown in Figure 3. It was clearly seen that the onset strain and the crack density of transverse crack was significantly affected by the edge finishing conditions. The transverse cracks were observed to entirely across the thickness and the width of 90 degree layers.

Onset strains of transverse crack and ultimate strains of laminates (B), (C), and (D) whose edges were differently sandpapered are shown in Figure 4. Finer edge specimens having smaller R_{max} tended to delay the crack onset strain and reduce the failure strain. A rougher edge finish (specimen B) can create additional defects which causes transverse cracking, whereas a finer edge finish (specimen D) can remove some defects induced by diamond wheel cut and consequently delay the

onset of transverse cracking. Transverse cracking process can be accelerated or decelerated depending on polishing conditions such as grain size, removed volume, etc.

Crack densities of specimen (A) and (E) as a function of tensile strain are shown in Figure 5. (Note the scale of Figure 3 and Figure 5 is different.) The grinding and milling finished specimen (E) having smaller R_{max} exhibited higher crack density and lower onset strain than the diamond wheel finished specimen (A). This result indicates machining variation as well as R_{max} can also affect the behavior of transverse crack. The conditions of grinding and milling employed to finish specimen (E) might have induced fine damages which was undetectable by the surface roughness measurements using the probe having radius of $0.1 \mu\text{m}$.

Ultimate strains of all the tested specimens as a function of crack density at 1.3% strain are shown in Figure 6. Crack densities at failure could not be identified because scanning speed of the remote microscope was limited. Interestingly, the ultimate strain of the specimens increased as the crack density increased. This result can be qualitatively explained in two ways. One is based on a fracture mechanics study in reference [10] and the other is edge and local delamination model proposed in reference [11].

Stress intensity factor (K_I) of isotropic semi-infinite plate having evenly spaced cracks (spacing interval = h , crack length = a) as depicted in Figure 7 is given to be $K = \sigma(h/2)^{1/2}$ when the ratio of crack length and crack spacing (a/h) is bigger than unit. Applying this analogy to $[0_2/90_4]_s$ laminate, it can be derived that shorter crack spacing can lower the stress intensity factor and consequently delays the total failure strain. Although the crack length in 0 degree layer was not experimentally obtained in this study, this discussion can be an adequate explanation of the above observation.

Edge and local delamination model schematically shown in Figure 8 can be also applicable to explain the above observation. In $[0_2/90_4]_s$ laminate the failure load is only sustained by 0 degree ply when the transverse cracks are isolated, local delamination mode in Figure 8 (b). On the other hand, the failure load is supported by both 0 and 90 degree ply if the transverse cracks are connected by delamination, edge delamination mode in Figure 8 (a). Higher crack density, or shorter crack distance, may create crack connections which eventually ends up to the edge delamination failure mode. Significant accumulation of transverse cracks can result in reducing stress concentration of 0 degree ply and letting the 90 degree ply play a role of supporting load at total failure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Edge finishing effects on transverse cracking under static tensile loading were studied using T800H/3631 $[0_2/90_4]_s$ cross-ply CFRP laminates. Following conclusions were made:

1. Edge finishing conditions significantly affect the onset strain and density of transverse crack.
2. Finer edge polish by sandpapering can delay onset of transverse crack and decrease accumulation of transverse crack.
3. Grinding and milling of specimen edge can induce fine damages which accelerate transverse cracking more than diamond wheel cutting.
4. Existence of transverse cracks does not necessarily result in a reduction of strength but can increase total failure strains of cross-ply laminates.

5. These results indicates that the edge finish conditions of composite test samples must be carefully considered in an analysis or comparison of available transverse crack data.

6. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Edge finishing methods of tested specimens and the maximum edge-surface roughness

Specimen	Edge Finishing Procedures* ¹	R _{max} (μm)
(A)	Non	2.3
(B)	#80 sandpapering	8.1
(C)	#400 sandpapering	2.9
(D)	Al ₂ O ₃ powder (φ= 5 and 0.05μm) polishing after #1000 and #2000 sandpapering	1.0
(E)	Hard metal milling* ² after diamond wheel grinding* ³	1.0

*₁; Before edge finishing all the spesimes were cut from a T800H/3631 laminate using a diamond wheel cutter (Grain size = #170, Cutting speed = 1600 m/min, Feeding rate = 200 mm/min)

*₂; Depth of cut = 0.05 mm, Cutting speed = 250 m/min, Feeding rate = 120 mm/min

*₃; Depth of cut = 0.5 mm, Cutting speed = 250 m/min, Feeding rate = 220 mm/min

L	L_G	L_{TP}	W	t	t_r	(mm)
300	127	10	25.4	1.73	1.8	

Figure 1. Test specimen configuration cut from a GFRP end-tabbed $[0_2/90_4]_s$ T800H/3631 laminate using diamond wheel cutter

Figure 2. Maximum edge-surface roughness (R_{max}) and width change (dW) of differently edge finished test specimens

Figure 3. Transverse crack accumulation of edge non-finished specimen, (A), and edge sandpapered specimens, (B), (C), and (D), as a function of tensile strain

Figure 4. Crack accumulation of diamond wheel finished specimen, (A), and hard metal milling finished specimen, (E)

Figure 5. Crack onset strain and ultimate strain of differently edge sandpapered specimens as a function of maximum edge-surface roughness

Figure 6. Ultimate tensile strain of differently edge finished T800H/3631 [0₂/90₄]_s laminates as a function of crack density at 1.3% strain

Figure 7. Stress intensity factor of semi-infinite plate having evenly spaced cracks [10]

Figure 8. Damage modes of cross-ply laminates proposed by O'Brien [11]